

The Impact of The Forced Transition from Face-to-Face to E-Learning on Students' Achievement in the Scientific Research Methodology Course

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the impact of the forced transition from face-to-face (f2f) to e-learning on students' achievement by comparing the marks of 102 students who studied the course of scientific research methods in two different ways (f2f vs. e-learning) and to know whether there were differences based on sex and academic year variables. The researcher utilized a descriptive approach and analytical procedures to achieve the study's objectives. Results indicated that the forced transition from face-to-face to e-learning had a negative impact on all students' achievement in e-learning as compared to f2f learning, on the achievement of male students when compared to female students, and on the achievement of older students when compared to younger ones, and this negative effect increases as students' progress in the academic years.

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Introduction

E-learning has become a popular tool in many educational institutions, regardless of its level, this due to its many benefits. It enables students to actively participate in what they are learning, makes them independent and able to access their learning anywhere and everywhere.

E-learning has become a popular tool in many educational institutions, regardless of its level, this due to its many benefits. It enables students to actively participate in what they are learning, makes them independent and able to access their learning anywhere and everywhere. That is, e-learning was not a result of the COVID-19 pandemic, but it was sometimes used as a supportive or individual method in many educational institutions. Before the pandemic, many of these universities were adopting one form or another of e-learning to teach some subjects and courses. Which means that the universities were prepared, albeit unevenly, to use this new method.

COVID-19 has necessitated the adoption of e-learning in higher education institutions as the substitute for traditional learning, to ensure that students complete and access their education under safe conditions.

Al-Quds Open University (as a university that adopts the blended learning style) was flexible in dealing with the coronavirus pandemic; this was evident in its success in switching from traditional face-to-face education to fully online learning when the epidemic intensified, which coincided with the middle of the second semester of the academic year (2019-2020). Its academic, administrative, and technological interventions led to the successful completion of the semester by holding online exams for the mid-semester courses and completing the semester online.

This issue (the forced transition from face-to-face learning to e-learning) has attracted researchers and instructors' attention. So many studies have dealt with this subject from different aspects and perspectives, and few of them targeted student achievement. The researcher, as a teacher of the scientific research methodology course, had believed that the transition to e-learning would not impact students' achievement, but he noticed that there was a clear discrepancy in students' marks in the midterm exam if compared to their marks in the final exam, which prompted him to study the impact of the forced transition from face-to-face to e-learning on students' achievement in this course. Therefore, and in order to understand how the forced transition from face-to-face learning to e-learning impacts the achievement of the students, the study will explore the following key question: "Does the forced transition from face-to-face learning to e-learning impact the students' achievement?" By answering a set of sub-questions.

Literature review

Previous literature

E-learning as a computer-assisted learning, is a collaborative learning approach centered on students, combines pedagogical aspects and computer-assisted, It is also based on delivering digital content and teaching in various forms. (Chitra& Raj, 2018) E-learning is also education based on modern methods of communication, such as the computer and its networks, various audiovisual materials, search engines, electronic libraries, and websites.

These methods can be used in the classroom or at a distance. (Pham et al., 2022). Moreover, e-learning is defined as learning that relies on the use of electronic media to achieve educational goals and deliver educational content to learners without regard to temporal and spatial barriers. (Al-Halafawi, 2006)

E-learning is a method of education that utilizes electronic media to deliver content to learners without any physical or temporal barriers. (Al-Halafawi, 2006). Or it can be considered a modern form of education that utilizes modern communication methods like computers, audiovisual materials, search engines, electronic libraries, and websites to achieve educational goals and deliver content without spatial or temporal barriers. (Chitra and Raj, 2018)

According to Khan (2005), e-learning is a learner-centered, creative, and interactive environment that uses digital technologies to enable anyone, anywhere, at any time, to access open, flexible, and distributed learning environments.

Chitra& Raj.(2018) believes that E-learning Concept Include various online, virtual, distributed, networked, and web-based educational activities conducted via electronic devices, including synchronous or asynchronous activities, and can be conducted online or offline.

However, Sangrà et al. (2012) argue that the definitions of e-learning should focus on four aspects: 1) technology-driven, 2) delivery system-oriented, 3) communication-oriented, and 4) instructional model-oriented.

Rodrigues et al. (2019) also consider e-learning as a broader approach to learning that brings new opportunities for learning and teaching in many fields of education far from the traditional classroom. They define it as an innovative web-based system based on digital technologies and other forms of educational materials whose primary goal is to provide students with a customized, learner-centered, open, enjoyable, and interactive learning environment that supports and enhances learning processes. Similarly, Hoppe et al. (2003) consider e-learning to be learning.

E-learning also has a variety of tools, ranging from synchronous e-learning to asynchronous e-learning, like video conferencing, chat rooms, virtual classrooms, white boards, email, the World Wide Web, mailing lists, discussion groups, file transfers, and CDs. (Al-Sayed, 2019) and various types like synchronous online learning, asynchronous online learning, computer-managed learning, computer-aided instruction, fixed e-learning, adaptive e-learning, linear e-learning, interactive online learning, individual online learning, and collaborative online learning. Asynchronous learning allows learners to access course material at their convenience, while synchronous learning involves real-time interaction. Computer-managed learning uses computers for assessment, while adaptive learning adapts to learners' preferences. Linear learning follows a sequential path, while interactive learning encourages active participation. Collaborative learning involves teamwork and cooperation among learners. (Avelino, J. 2023)

As for the importance of e-learning (Millham et al. 2014) indicates that eLearning is fundamental for enhancing learners' performance, engagement, self-regulation, flexibility, interest, and motivation. Active participation and self-regulated learning are facilitated by it, resulting in the attainment of desired learning outcomes through construction, learning-pace adjustment, and active participation.

As far as the advantages and disadvantages of using e-learning, E-learning in university education offers many benefits like improved communication, skill development, and enjoyable scientific materials. However, it can also promote social isolation due to increased screen time, requiring careful consideration and balance. (Al Rawashdeh, 2021).

Previous Studies:

Previous studies have compared both face-to-face and e-learning to explore their impact on student achievement.

Hammoud et al.'S (2021) study on the effectiveness and challenges of distance learning found no differences in students' arithmetic mean based on gender, college, or course nature.

While Abu Shkheidim, S., et al. (2020) found moderate effectiveness of e-learning in coping with the spread of the Corona virus.

Basilaia and Kvavadze's (2020) study confirmed the successful transition to online education, highlighting the potential for future use of the gained experience in the case of missed lessons.

Bir's D.D. (2019) study found that online teaching may have a negative impact on students' academic performance compared to face-to-face classes.

Dendir's (2019) study reveals that online students perform better on tests, but self-selection affects their performance, and according to assessments that measure higher learning, assessments show lower performance.

Another study by Dendir (2016) revealed a significant difference in academic performance between online and face-to-face classes, with online students generally scoring higher on assessments.

The Tseng and Walsh (2016) study sought to compare and evaluate students' perceptions and experiences in both blended and traditional courses. The study found that blended students have higher overall learning motivation and higher outcomes than those in the traditional course, but overall satisfaction remained unchanged. Badaran and Aqil's (2015) study found that e-learning methods significantly improved the achievement of students in a grammar course compared to traditional methods.

The Motii and Sanders Study (2014) found that online instructional modes performed at least as well as traditional (face-to-face) classes in terms of overall semester grades.

The Al-Qahtani & Higgins Study (2012) showed that there is a difference between the three methods and found that blended learning outperformed traditional learning in terms of student achievement, while e-learning and traditional learning groups showed no significant difference.

Abu-Akl's Study (2012) showed that there were differences in favor of the group that was taught by e-learning in the achievement test, at the level of gender, and in favor of females.

Ibrahim's (2010) study demonstrated the effective impact of e-learning on student achievement, with no significant difference in achievement between experimental and control groups, regardless of sex.

Ali and Hassoun's (2009) study demonstrated that e-learning outperforms classical methods in achieving better results, and recommended the use of this method when the appropriate capabilities are available for the results achieved.

Holm et al. (2003) found the WEBCT system enhances traditional education, but is not a substitute and showed no differences based on student gender, college, or age.

Finally, it should be noted that previous studies have not clearly indicated a preference for distance or face-to-face teaching, nor have they provided conclusive evidence on their impact on student achievement.

The purpose of the Study

The study aimed to determine the impact of the forced transition from face-to-face (f2f) to e-learning teaching on students' achievement by comparing the academic achievement of Al-Quds Open University students in the Scientific Research Methodology course using (f2f) vs. e-learning and to know whether this effect differs according to the variables of the student's sex and his academic year. This will be done by answering the main research question and sub-questions as follows:

- Does the forced transition from face-to-face to e-learning impact students' achievement?
- Does the Academic Achievement of Al-Quds Open University Students Differ in the Course of Scientific Research Methods in Traditional Education (f2f) Versus E-Learning?
- Does the Impact of the Forced Transition from Face-to-Face to E-Learning on Students' Achievement Differ According to the Student's Sex?
- Does the Impact of the Forced Transition from Face-to-Face to E-Learning on Students' Achievement Differ According to the Student's Academic Year?

Methodology of the Study

The researcher followed the steps of the descriptive approach and analytical procedures, where the study was based on the students' marks in midterm and final exams; the data were analyzed using frequencies and percentages.

Population and Sampling

The population of the study is represented by 460 students of Al-Quds Open University (QOU) who registered in the second semester of the academic year (2019–2020) in the Scientific Research Methods course. Based on the size of the study population, 102 students were randomly selected as a sample for this study. It was represented by the students of Sections 1, 6, and 11, for a total of 117. 15 students were excluded for not meeting the conditions. The table and figures below show the demographic characteristics of the sample.

Table 1

The Demographic Characteristics of the Sample

The Year	Sex	N	Percentage
First Year	Females	30	0.294
	Males	9	0.088
	Sum	39	0.382
Second Year	Females	21	0.205
	Males	7	0.068

	Sum	28	0.274
Third Year	Females	16	0.156
	Males	6	0.058
	Sum	22	0.216
Fourth Year	Females	8	0.078
	Males	5	0.049
	Sum	13	0.127
Total		102	Percentage

Table 1 shows that the percentages of students in the study sample are not equal according to sex. Rather, most of the members of the study sample were females, as they constitute 0.735 for females and 0.265 for males, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

The distribution of sample students, according to sex.

It also exhibits that the percentage of students is not equal in academic years, as their distribution came in a row (38% in the first year, 27% in the second year, 21% in the third, and 13% in the fourth year), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure2

The distribution of the sample students, according to the academic year

Procedure of the Study

The data collection procedure was conducted using the students' marks in each of the midterm and final exams in the second semester of the academic year (2019–2020). The participants were the students taking the scientific research methods course.

Instruments of the Study

The study relied on the tests used by the university to evaluate students, which are:

- Electronic midterm exams, which covered the first half of the course material and were taught face-to-face.
- Electronic final exams, which covered the second half of the course material and were taught electronically.

Noting that the midterm and final exams have the same characteristics, each of them consists of thirty objective questions that the student answers electronically within sixty minutes.

Reliability and Validity

The researcher did not perform any procedures related to validity and reliability, because the study relied on the tests used by the university to evaluate students and on the assumption that these tests have acceptable levels of validity and reliability.

Variables of the Study

The current study included two types of variables:

- 1- The independent variable was the mode of instruction (traditional (face-to-face) or e-learning).
- 2- The dependent variable was academic achievement, measured by the average marks of the midterm and final exams of the scientific research methods course.

Data Analysis

The data of this study were analyzed by calculating the arithmetic means and percentages of the students' marks in each midterm and final exam of the scientific research methods course to express the academic achievement of the students and were also used to verify the effect of student sex and academic year.

Results & Discussion

The results related to the first question, " Does the academic achievement of Al-Quds Open University students differ in the course of scientific research methods in traditional education (f2f) versus e-learning?"Table2

The results of the first question

N	Mean of midterm marks	Mean of final marks
102	75.412	63.942

The table above shows that the arithmetic mean for the student's marks in the midterm exam was (75.412) and was in the final exam (63.942). In other words, their achievement in (f2f) was higher than their achievement in e-learning, as the difference between their arithmetic mean in the midterm and final exams reached 11.47 degrees.

So, it can be said that the forced transition from (f2f) to e-learning had a negative impact on students' achievement in e-learning compared to (f2f) learning. This may refer to the fact that students are accustomed to f2f; in addition, the quick transition to e-learning didn't allow enough time for the students to get acquainted with the nature of e-learning in this context and gain sufficient experience to deal with e-learning.

This result corresponds with a study by Abu Shkheidim, (2020), which revealed that the effectiveness of e-learning in light of the spread of the coronavirus was moderate. And with a study by Bir, D.D. (2019), which found that online teaching may have negative effects on students' academic performance when compared to the performance of students in (f2f) classes, and with a study by Holm et al. (2003), which concluded that the (WEBCT) system was not a substitute for traditional education,

On the other hand, this result contradicts the results of studies by Holm et al. (2003), Ali and Hassoun (2009), Ibrahim, study (2010), Al-Badaran, M., and Abu Akl, S. (2015), Motii and Sanders Study (2014), Dendir (2016), Aljaser (2019), Basilaia, and Kvavadze's case study (2020) that showed the effectiveness of e-learning compared to (f2f).

5:2. The results related to the second question, "Does the impact of the forced transition from face-to-face to e-learning on students' achievement differ according to the student's sex?"

Table3

The results of the second question

sex	N	mean of midterm marks	mean of final marks
M	27	73.29	58.90
F	75	77.55	68.99
Total	102	75.42	63.94

The table above shows that the arithmetic mean for male students' marks in the midterm exam was 73.29, while it reached 58.90 in the final. As for the arithmetic mean for females, it reached 77.55 in the midterm and 68.99 in the final, as shown in Figure 3.

Figure3

The marks of the students according to sex in midterm and final exams

So, it can be said that the forced transition from face-to-face (f2f) to e-learning teaching had a negative impact on students' achievement and had a more negative impact on the achievement of male students compared to females. This may be referred to as the fact that females constitute the majority of the sample and the population, and perhaps their interest in switching to e-learning is greater than that of their male colleagues; this result contradicts Holm et al. (2003), who showed no differences due to the variable of sex.

5:3. The results related to the third question, "Does the Impact of the Forced Transition from Face-to-Face to E-Learning on Students' Achievement Differ According to the Student's Academic Year?"

Table 4

The results of examining the third question

The table above shows that the arithmetic mean for first-year students in the midterm exam was 76, while it was 69.5 in the final. At the level of second year students, their arithmetic mean in the midterm exam was 70.5 and 61.64 in the final. Regarding third-year students, the arithmetic mean in the midterm was 77.5 and in the final was 66.85. As for the fourth-year students, their arithmetic mean in the midterm exam was 77.5 and in the final 57.54, as shown in Figure 4.

Figure4

The marks of the students according to academic year in midterm and final exams

So, it can be said that the forced transition from face-to-face (f2f) to e-learning teaching had a negative impact on students' achievement, and this negative impact increases with students' progress in the academic years.

By discussing this result, it is noted that these differences increased with the progress of students in the academic years, as the difference between the students' score two exams (midterm and final) at the level of first-year students was six degrees, nine degrees at the level of the second year, eleven degrees at the level of third-year students, and twenty degrees at the level of fourth-year students. Perhaps this indicates that the younger students are more ready to be convinced and accept e-learning and that the older students are accustomed to (f2f) and are not interested in e-learning.

Limitations of the Study

This study has many limitations that should be considered.

- The study was applied to Al-Quds Open University students, the Jenin branch, who were enrolled in the scientific research methodology course in the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020.

- The students learned half of the course material (f2f) way, and they had to complete the second half online when the pandemic intensified and educational institutions had to close their doors.
- Students' marks in the midterm and final exams of the course were adopted as indicators of their achievement.

Conclusion

As a result of the previous presentation, the study concludes that:

- The Transition from Face-to-Face (f2f) to E-Learning Significantly Had a Negative Impact on Students' Achievement in E-Learning Compared to (f2f) Learning By assessing student achievement based on their midterm (which measures their learning (f2f)) and final exam (which measures their learning using e-learning), it was discovered that their achievement in (f2f) is better than in e-learning.
- The Forced Transition from Face-to-Face Teaching to Online Learning Had a Greater Negative Impact on the Achievement of Male Students Compared to Female Students.
- The Forced Transition from Face-to-Face (f2f) to E-Learning Teaching Has a More Negative Impact on Older Students' Achievement Compared to Younger Ones. This Negative Effect Increases as Students' Progress in the Academic Years.

Recommendations

Taking into account the researcher's earlier findings, he put forth a set of recommendations that highlight:

- 1- The need for adequate preparation before introducing a new teaching method
- 2- It is crucial to provide and offer the appropriate materials, equipment, techniques, programs, etc. for the new teaching method.
- 3- Teachers and students must equip themselves with increased technological proficiency for teaching based on the new teaching method.
- 4- Teachers should actively assume their responsibilities and establish a positive relationship with students to encourage them to adopt the new teaching approach.
- 5- Teachers must encourage students to work together to learn and excel in the new teaching method.
- 6- Administrators must ensure that students are prepared and ready for the new teaching method.

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The researcher asserts that there are no conflicts of interest in the publication of this research.

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